

CODEN (USA): IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ANATOMICAL AND HISTOPATHOLOGICAL EVALUATION
OF LARGE INTESTINAL TUMORS****Dr. Zubair Ahmed Yousfani¹, Dr. Jabeen Atta², Dr. Imran Karim³,
Dr. Hamid Nawaz Ali Memon⁴, Dr. Samar Raza³ and Dr. Zulfiqar Ali Qutrio Baloch⁵**¹Department of Surgery, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences (LUMHS).²Department of Gynecology & Obstetrics, Bilawal Medical College, LUMHS Jamshoro.³Department of Medicine, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences (LUMHS).⁴Zulekha Hospital, Dubai United Arab Emirates.⁵Brandon Regional Hospital, Brandon, Florida.**Received:** 27February 2016**Accepted:** 10 March 2017**Published:** 14 March 2017**Abstract:****OBJECTIVE:** To evaluate the anatomical and histopathological pattern of large intestinal tumors**PATIENTS AND METHODS:** This descriptive case series study of two years was conducted at Liaquat University Hospital Hyderabad. The inclusion criteria of the study were patients ≥ 12 years of age, either gender, diagnosed as large intestine malignancy were recruited and enrolled in the study. All surgically resected intestinal specimens were grossly observed and after kept in 10% formalin sent to laboratory for histopathological examination. The data was recorded on pre-designed proforma and analyzed in SPSS 16. The frequency, percentages and mean \pm SD was computed for study variables.**RESULTS:** During two year study period, total 30 patients diagnosed as intestinal malignancy. The mean age \pm SD for whole population was 58.75 ± 6.51 with female gender predominance. The rectal malignancy was commonly observed 15 (40%) followed by transverse colon 3(10%). The adenocarcinoma was predominant 22 (73.3%) well differentiates 24 (80%) and ulcero-infiltrative 12 (40%) pattern.**CONCLUSION:** Tumors of the digestive tract show a wide variation in the anatomical and histological type, thus early evaluation is beneficial for appropriate management.**Keywords:** Intestinal tumors, Rectum carcinoma and Histopathology.**Corresponding Author:****Dr. Zubair Ahmed Yousfani***

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Please cite this article in press as Zubair Ahmed Yousfani et al, *Anatomical and Histopathological Evaluation of Large Intestinal Tumors*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2017; 4(3).

INTRODUCTION:

Gastrointestinal tumors account for a large proportion of all neoplasm, colorectal cancer ranks second among the most common malignancy worldwide [1-3]. Despite the length and vast pool of dividing cells the small intestine is still an uncommon site for tumor [4]. There is world wide variation in the distribution of these tumors that are due to exogenous factors rather than genetical [5]. The different histologic type of tumor at various gastrointestinal regions also differs in their prognosis and incidence [6]. The neoplasm arising from the mucosa intestines predominate over stromal and mesenchymal tumours [7-9]. Adenocarcinomas constitute 80% of all malignancies of gastrointestinal tract. Without any exception, all neoplasm with time metastasis and are incurable [10,11]. However effective and appropriate treatment in stromal tumors and lymphoma is likely to result in cure [12,13]. This study was planned to determine the frequency of various histopathologic types of neoplasm of intestines and knowledge about their occurrence will aid the health care provider in effective management of patient.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This descriptive case series study of two years was conducted at Liaquat University Hospital Hyderabad. The inclusion criteria of the study were patients ≥ 12 years of age, either gender, diagnosed as large intestine malignancy were recruited and enrolled in the study. After taken informed consent, the detail history was taken along with specific clinical examination, the relevant investigations were advised and the subjects were managed accordingly. All surgically resected intestinal specimens were grossly observed and after kept in 10% formalin sent to laboratory for histopathological examination. The exclusion criteria of the study were all non neoplastic lesions of intestines and biopsy specimens and non cooperative patients. The data was recorded on pre-designed proforma and analyzed in SPSS 16. The frequency, percentages and mean \pm SD was computed for study variables.

RESULTS:

During two year study period, total 30 patients diagnosed as intestinal malignancy. The mean age \pm SD for whole population was 58.75 ± 6.51 with female gender predominance. The results of the study are mentioned in Table 1-2.

Table 01: Demographical, Anatomical and Histological Distribution of the Population

AGE (yrs)	N= 30	PERCENTAGE (%)
30-39	3	10
40-49	5	16.6
50-59	12	40
60+	10	33.3
GENDER		
Male	20	66.6
Female	10	33.3
ANATOMICAL DISTRIBUTION		
Caecum	06	20
Ascending Colon	02	6.6
Transverse Colon	03	10
Descending Colon	02	6.6
Sigmoid Colon	01	3.3
Rectum	15	50
Anal canal	01	3.3
HISTOLOGICAL VARIANT		
Adenocarcinoma	22	73.3
Mucinous adenocarcinoma	05	16.6
Adenosquamous Carcinoma	03	10

Table 02: The Gross Appearances and Differentiation of Masses

DIFFERENTIATION	N = 30	PERCENTAGE (%)
Well	24	80
Moderate	04	13.3
Poor	02	6.6
GROSS APPEARANCE		
Polypoid	04	13.3
Ulceroinfiltrative	12	40
Ulceroinproliferative	10	33.3
Fungating	04	13.3

DISCUSSION:

Tumors of the colon and rectum are the commonest tumors in the gastrointestinal tract, however, in Pakistan these malignancies are relatively uncommon but its incidence is increasing and varies from place. In the present series, 30 patients had tumor at colorectal region with female predominance consistent with the study by Prabhakar BR, et al[14]. Colorectal carcinomas were seen over an age range from 30 to 60 years with the peak occurrence in the 5th decade which is consistent to other studies by Devi KR et al[15] and Prabhakar BR et al[14] observed peak occurrence was 5th decade, although it was observed to be in 7th decade by Abdulkareem FB, et al[16]. The female predominance also consistent with the study by Mohammad A, et al[17] although Jackson-Thompson J, et al[18], shown male gender predominance with non significant statistical analysis. Diet is known to play a key role in the etiology of colorectal tumor and of the thirty individuals, 25 patients had mixed diet and 5 had vegetable diet and it was noticed that increased incidence of colorectal cancer in patients having mixed diet [19,20]. Clinically patients presented with variable signs and symptoms depending on the lesion type and its anatomical location. The commonest was intestinal obstruction, abdominal discomfort, bleeding per rectum and constipation [21]. The anatomical site commonly involved was rectum, constituting 15 (50%) of colorectal malignancies consistent with the studies by Devi KR, et al[15] and Abdulkareem FB, et al[16] while the study by Eisenberg N, et al shown left colon as the predominant site of origin of tumor [22]. The commonest growth pattern was ulcerative forms 12 (40%) distributed all over colon and rectum. The other forms observed were polypoid 4 (13.3%) and fungating masses 4 (13.3%). The observations are related to the former studies [23, 24]. The histological study showed well differentiated adenocarcinomas which is also consistent with study by Abdulkareem FB, et al[16]. In current series

majority of the patients (80%) presented at an advanced stage of cancer. Tumor of anal canal region was reported in one patient as adenocarcinoma occurring in old female presented as a polypoidal mass. The literature regarding anal canal malignancy was also conducted by Salati SA, et al[25].

CONCLUSION:

Tumors of the digestive tract show a wide variation in the anatomical and histological type, so early evaluation and treatment is beneficial for appropriate treatment and is supportive to provide better quality of life to the patient.

REFERENCES:

1. Quante M, Varga J, Wang TC, Greten FR. The gastrointestinal tumor microenvironment. *Gastroenterology*. 2013 Jul;145(1):63-78
2. Joensuu H, Hohenberger P, Corless CL. Gastrointestinal stromal tumour. *Lancet*. 2013 Sep 14;382(9896):973-83
3. Atrkar-Roushan Z, Kazemnejad A, Mansour-Ghanaei F, Zayeri F. Trend analysis of gastrointestinal cancer incidences in Guilan province: comparing rates over 15 years. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*. 2013;14(12):7587-93.
4. Serban DE. Gastrointestinal cancers: influence of gut microbiota, probiotics and prebiotics. *Cancer Lett*. 2014 Apr 10;345(2):258-70
5. Selikoff IJ. Epidemiology of gastrointestinal cancer. *Environ Health Perspect*. 1974 Dec; 9: 299-305.
6. Boland CR. The Molecular Biology of Gastrointestinal Cancer: Implications for Diagnosis and Therapy. *Gastrointest Endosc Clin N Am*. 2008 Jul; 18(3):401-7
7. Pourhoseingholi MA, Vahedi M, Baghestani AR. Burden of gastrointestinal cancer in Asia; an overview. *Gastroenterol Hepatol Bed Bench*. 2015 Winter; 8(1): 19-27.

- 8.Ladd AP, Grosfeld JL. Gastrointestinal tumors in children and adolescents. *Semin Pediatr Surg.* 2006 Feb;15(1):37-47.
- 9.Greenlee HB, Aranha GV, DeOrio AJ. Neoplastic obstruction of the small and large intestine. *Curr Probl Cancer.* 1979 Aug;4(2):1-49.
- 10.Terzic J, Grivennikov S, Karin E, Karin M. Inflammation and colon cancer. *Gastroenterology.* 2010 Jun;138(6):2101-2114.e5.
- 11.Fleming M, Ravula S, Tatishev SIF, Wang HL. Colorectal carcinoma: Pathologic aspects. *J Gastrointest Oncol.* 2012 Sep; 3(3): 153–173.
- 12.Makinen MJ. Colorectal serrated adenocarcinoma. *Histopathology.* 2007 Jan;50(1):131-50.
- 13.Park JS, Huh JW, Park YA, Cho YB, Yun SH, Kim HC, et al. Prognostic comparison between mucinous and nonmucinous adenocarcinoma in colorectal cancer. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2015 Apr;94(15):e658.
- 14.Prabhakar BR, Prabhakar H, Tung BS. Gastrointestinal Malignant tumors in Amristsar (Punjab). *Indian Journal of Surgery* 1981; 343-345
- 15.Devi KR, Suvarna N. Pattern of gastrointestinal tumours in North Kerala. *Indian J Cancer.* 1980 Sep;17(3):159-63.
- 16.Abdulkareem FB, Abudu EK, Awolola NA, Elesha SO, Rotimi O, et al. Colorectal carcinoma in Lagos and Sagamu, Southwest Nigeria: A histopathological review. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2008 Nov 14; 14(42): 6531–6535.
- 17.Mohammad A, Makaju R. Retrospective histopathological analysis of various neoplasms of different parts of the gastrointestinal tract seen at the Kathmandu University Teaching Hospital, Dhulikhel, Nepal. *Kathmandu University Medical Journal* 2006;4: 474-478
- 18.Jackson-Thompson J, Ahmed F, German RR, Lai SM, Friedman C. Descriptive epidemiology of colorectal cancer in the United States, 1998-2001. *Cancer.* 2006 Sep 1;107(5 Suppl):1103-11.
- 19.Ryan-Harshman M, Aldoori W. Diet and colorectal cancer: review of the evidence. *Can Fam Physician.* 2007 Nov; 53(11): 1913–1920.
- 20.Hou N, Huo D, Dignam JJ. Prevention of colorectal cancer and dietary management. *Chin Clin Oncol.* 2013 Jun; 2(2): 13.
- 21.Cappell MS. Pathophysiology, clinical presentation, and management of colon cancer. *Gastroenterol Clin North Am.* 2008 Mar;37(1):1-24,
- 22.Eisenberg N, Decosse JJ. Carcinoma of the colon and rectum. *Cancer* 1982;49:1131.
- 23.Ueno H, Mochizuki H, Hashiguchi Y, Ishiguro M, Kajiwaraya Y, Sato T, et al. Histological grading of colorectal cancer: a simple and objective method. *Ann Surg.* 2008 May;247(5):811-8
- 24.Ponz de Leon M, Di Gregorio C. Pathology of colorectal cancer. *Dig Liver Dis.* 2001 May;33(4):372-88.
- 25.Salati SA, Kadi AA. Anal cancer - a review. *Int J Health Sci (Qassim).* 2012 Jun; 6(2): 206–230.